

A STUDY ON THE TRENDS AND PROBLEMS OF CAMPUS RECRUITMENT IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN COIMBATORE – With Special Reference to Engineering Institutions

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Abstract:

In the decade past, the corporates were in need of help from the campus placement cell of the educational institutions to post their status in the bulletin board of the college campus. They work to get flood of applications from the college graduating students. But it is changed today. The demand of the students is high. Because of the stagnant recruiting budget of the corporates and their outdated recruitment process is not offering much excitement in the minds of the graduating students. The hiring authority should be creative and their position should create a pack with success in the recruitment process to hire high standard of students. This is a very critical task to control over the on-campus recruitment program's budgets. The India Skills Report 2014 says that according to the Industry sector the sourcing channel preferences varied, while the BPO/ITES and Manufacturing sectors' got only 16.81% candidates from the campuses hires. The today's generations are expecting learn to enjoy their work at the workplace. But the reality differs. They should be flexible with the workplace/organizational culture. Many educational institutions are offering attractive courses for the students which give enjoyment during their learning period. This also will help to enjoy their work later. The internships are the crucial part of their courses. Students have to understand that no field is glamorous. The creation of any particular field as glamour is only an assumption of them. But the reality is far from their assumption. Hence, the present study is focusing on the trends and problems of campus recruitment in the educational institutions of Coimbatore. The study confined its research only to the Engineering Educational Institutions. The study is completed with the help of both primary and secondary sources of the data collections.

Key Words: Flood of Applications, Outdated Recruiting Processes, On-Campus Presence & Assumption-Reality and Ambitious.

Introduction:

The Engineering Educational Institutions are serving the knowledge to its students about the professional practice of engineering. This practice of teaching includes from the basic education to the advanced education of all the particular fields of specialization. The students who are passing out from the Engineering Educational Institutions are coming with the knowledge to fulfill the expectations and requirements of the high standard modern business world. Today, the unemployment ratio is equal with the output of engineering graduates and the trend is getting increased. The unemployment may also create a gap between the practical and the technical knowledge. The practical knowledge by the Engineering Educational Institutions may not equalize with the technical knowledge of the business world.

The corporates are looking for Gen Y talents which are investing in a strong way. They also were expecting the ingenious campus program by mapping out the criteria for

the domestic engineering educational institutions for participating in the campus hiring plan. Half of the Indian organization is expecting for the better student and faculty ratio, permanent faculty, infrastructure, accreditation, media report, reputation of the institution, *quality of students* and to have a good number of / pool of experienced candidates. Many criterion is differing from one institution to another and they are research published by the faculty members (permanent), industry experience of visiting faculty, alumni network and the performance of the placed students from campus. The demand pattern of the industries and the educational institutions is getting massive change. The change has resulted in paradigm shift in the selection of guidelines of the educational institutions and the recruiting industry¹.

A decent Engineering Institutions should have assured placements with lots of hard work, assignments, live projects, and competitive atmosphere. The Four-year stint at a good Engineering Institutions is a self-discovery journey, with live projects, assignments, research works, presentations with appropriate testing and evaluation. The failures and achievements are going hand in hand since failures are stepping stone to success. The product comes out more shiny and bright, tough and resilient and above all, much more dynamic and flexible, and by the end of academics, most of the students realize the exact need for the life. But the career choice becomes a dilemma and they solve it with both logic and heart, without getting swayed away by the opinions. The most challenging phase of an Engineering Institutions student is the time of placements. A knowledge aspirant who joins the management schools with projected ambitions coupled with expectations makes the task difficult during the time of placements. Needless to say even the most reputed Engineering Institutions are facing problems for placing the right candidate at the right organization.

In the present scenario the concept of 'dream job' is getting absent. It is not a big deal to work in a Multi-National Companies and/or going to abroad for a project. But the matter is the students want to master themselves, in the areas like the profile of the job and the responsibility towards the job. The major numbers of students are forced by the business world to see the other images of their own in their mirror. This is because of every milestone is faced through the numerous psychological forces, cultural forces and also from the socioeconomic forces. This is the biggest challenges to the job seekers and also the recruiters².

Operational Definitions:

The Recruitment is a process of "searching for the potential workers and filtering, stimulating and encouraging the job seekers to apply for the jobs in an entity".

Campus Recruitment defines as "any efforts made by the potential recruiters to hire the students from the College campuses. This will be usually given the priority to the graduates. The recruiters using the campuses of the educational institutions from its campus recruitment for attracting and screening the students for different varieties of positions. This can be for both interns and as well as the full time job seekers".

Campus Recruitment:

Campus Recruitment is the process of job placement program and the activities are administered by the Educational Institutions for their graduating students. Many perspective recruiters are visiting the premises of the universities to meet and hire the outstanding graduates for their job openings. The main component of the Campus

¹ Hatcher, L., Kryter, K., Prus, J. S., & Fitzgerald, V. (1992). Predicting college student satisfaction, commitment and attrition from investment model constructs. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 22(16), 1273-1296

² Patro, C.S. (2013). Human Resource Management: An Optimistic Approach at the time of Recession *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 9(6), 37-41.

Placement Program is *Job Fairs* and it facilitates interviews. This also facilitates the information sharing sessions between the perspective recruiters and the graduating students. This will encourage the students to attend the on-campus job hiring programs in the professional attire with complete prepared resume in hand. The students are also prepared for the potential on spot job interviews. The main aim of the Campus Hiring Program by the Educational Institutions and the Organization is to prepare the students and to give the job search advantages. With the help of the on-campus job fairs (one of the campus recruiting program), a graduating college student can have a good interaction with the potential recruiters and can come to know the need, demand and expectations of them. They can have the better sense of their employment opportunities and the choices. Many recruitment events are allowing the students to have a better exposure to the wide variety of perspective recruiters through site like niche. Multiple on-spot campus recruitment (i.e. Job Fairs) will help the students as well as the recruiters to save their time, transportation costs and energy which are very vital in the case of recruiters based on their and in other regions³.

The students should be well prepared and planned in advance to make the Campus Placement Program as a successful one. They should visit the College Career Planning or the Placement Office Cell or the Websites of all the colleges at earliest of on the academic year which will help to obtain a list of upcoming Programs of the Campus Placements. It is highly recommended to the students to have a research on the perspective recruiters' list which will make them to become familiar with the brand, products and services of all the business organization before they enter into the Campus Placement Job Fair. It is highly notable thing by the recruiters, the students' engagement with the prospective employers through the intelligent conversations about their own strengths and the experiences.⁴

Current Trends of the Campus Recruitment Process:

Following are the current trends of the campus recruitment process⁵:

Busier Campus Hiring Programs:

The expectations of College Career Centers are with the number of companies come to the campus are more than ever. Many of the colleges have seen they are getting more number of companies in their campus comparatively with the last three years' record. It is a high record break i.e. More than 25% of the colleges are having 250 different companies as their campus recruiters for a year. It is getting increased. Some time with less time for a students, the organizational professionals are missing the opportunities to have a connect with the top talented students.

Many Colleges Missing the Marks on the Preparation of Students:

Many corporates are concerned about the Career Service Department of the various Engineering Educational Institutions and their out dated approach with the students. Some of the Engineering Institutions do not believe in the social media. They are not accepting the social media as a valuable one or it has an opportunity in the hiring/recruiting process. Many institutions are focusing and undergoing research about their students' resume training and training for interview. It is revealed by the corporate recruiting teams that the students in many Engineering Educational Institutions are not very successful in the preparation of resume and the interview preparation.

³ <http://www.campusinteraction.com/blog/>

⁴ <http://edupedia.educarnival.com/internship-report-on-hrm-practices-of-bankingsector-a-casestudy-on-uttara-bank> [Accessed 10-12-13]

⁵ Kotler, P., & Fox, K. F. (1995). Strategic marketing for educational institutions Englewood Cliffs: Prentice Hall.

There is a Disconnection Between the Career Services Department of Engineering Educational Institutions and the Hiring Trend of the Corporates Today:

One of the major implication causes for this disconnection between the Career Services Department of the Engineering Educational Institutions and the hiring trend of the today's corporates is the technologic development and changes. The corporate recruiters feel that the educational institutions are not matching with the fore seek trend of the hiring companies. And many of the educational institutions are failed to train their students for the latest technological development. The day-by-day technology for the Human Resource is getting / moving faster than ever. To reality the departments of placement in Engineering Educational Institutions do not know the real need of the recruiters and the training methods to the students.

Recruiting at Campus is a Time Consuming Process:

The recruiters are expecting to meet a wide number of students but the time and the budget are not permitting. Many companies lack in time and also in budget, they really need to be effective on campus in the hiring process. The real fact is that nearly one third of the companies do not have dedicated staff as the campus recruiters. It is decided by the companies in 2016 the interns should increase and planned to hire more graduates. The major problem/challenge identified by the recruiters is to access more talent in less time.

Objective:

To identify the problem associated with the Skill Gap Campus Recruitment in the Educational Institutions in Coimbatore.

Methodology:

Data:

The data required for the study is primary in nature. The primary data is collected by employing the Questionnaire.

Framework of Analysis:

The collected data are analyzed by making use of the Chi-Square Test and Correlation analysis.

Hypothesis of the Study:

Following NULL hypothesis are framed for the studies and tested:

H₀¹ – There is no significant relationship between the Gender and Skill Gap of the Students.

H₀² – There is no significant relationship between the Age and Skill Gap of the Students.

H₀³ – There is no significant relationship between the Career Aspirations and Skill Gap of the Students.

H₀⁴ – There is no significant relationship between the Locality of the Students and Skill Gap of the Students.

H₀⁵ – There is no significant relationship between the Department/Course and Skill Gap of the Students.

Analysis Part of the Study:

Table 1: Chi-square analysis for Skill Gap of the Students and Gender of the Respondents

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E
7	5.67	1.33	1.77	0.312
5	2.7	2.3	5.29	1.959
12	14.04	-2.04	4.16	0.296
3	4.59	-1.59	2.53	0.551
14	15.33	-1.33	1.77	0.115
5	7.3	-2.3	5.29	0.724
40	37.96	2.04	4.16	0.109

14	12.41	1.59	2.53	0.203
Total				4.269

Degree of freedom = $(r-1)(c-1) = (2-1)(4-1) = 3$

The table value of χ^2 for the degree of freedom 3 at 5% level of significance is 7.815. The calculated value of χ^2 is 4.269 which is less than the table value, therefore the null hypothesis is **Accepted**. Hence, it is inferred there is No Significant relationship between the variables.

Table 2: Chi-square analysis for Skill Gap of the Students and Age of the Respondents

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E
13	12.18	0.82	0.672	0.055
4	5.8	0.689	0.475	0.082
36	30.16	5.84	34.10	1.13
5	9.86	1.13	1.27	0.129
2	6.51	-4.51	20.34	3.124
4	3.1	0.9	0.81	0.261
14	16.12	-2.12	.49	0.27
11	5.27	5.73	32.83	6.230
1	0.84	0.16	0.025	0.030
2	2.08	-0.08	0.0064	0.003
1	0.68	0.32	0.1024	0.15
5	1.47	3.53	12.46	8.47
2	0.7	1.3	1.69	2.414
Total				22.348

Degree of freedom = $(r-1)(c-1) = (4-1)(4-1) = 9$

The table value of χ^2 for the degree of freedom 9 at 5% level of significance is 16.919. The calculated value of χ^2 is 22.348 which is more than the table value, therefore the null hypothesis is **Rejected**. Hence, it is inferred there is a Significant relationship between the variables.

Table 3: Chi-square analysis for Skill Gap of the Students and Career Aspirations of the Respondents

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E
2	2.73	-0.73	0.532	0.194
10	6.76	3.24	10.49	1.552
1	2.21	-1.21	1.464	0.662
19	18.27	0.73	0.532	0.029
10	8.7	1.3	1.69	0.194
42	45.24	-3.24	10.49	0.2332
16	14.79	1.21	1.464	0.098
Total				2.961

Degree of freedom = $(r-1)(c-1) = (2-1)(4-1) = 3$

The table value of χ^2 for the degree of freedom 3 at 5% level of significance is 7.815. The calculated value of χ^2 is 2.961 which is less than the table value, therefore the null hypothesis is **Accepted**. Hence, it is inferred there is No Significant relationship between the variables.

Table 4: Chi-square analysis for Skill Gap of the Students and Locality of the Respondents

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E
2	2.73	-0.73	0.532	0.195
10	6.76	3.24	10.49	1.552
1	2.21	-1.21	1.464	0.662
18	15.33	2.67	7.128	0.465
7	7.3	-0.3	0.09	0.012
35	37.96	-2.96	8.76	0.230

13	12.41	0.59	0.348	0.028
1	2.94	-1.94	3.76	1.280
3	1.4	1.6	2.56	1.828
7	7.28	-0.28	0.078	0.010
3	2.38	0.62	0.384	0.161
Total				6.423

Degree of freedom = (r-1) (c-1) = (3-1) (4-1) = 6

The table value of χ^2 for the degree of freedom 6 at 5% level of significance is 12.592. The calculated value of χ^2 is 6.423 which is less than the table value, therefore the null hypothesis is **Accepted**. Hence, it is inferred there is No Significant relationship between the variables.

Table 5: Chi-square analysis for Skill Gap of the Students and Department/Course of the Respondents

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E
10	7.56	2.44	5.95	0.78
4	7.28	-3.28	10.75	1.47
10	10.36	-0.36	0.12	0.012
4	2.8	1.2	1.44	0.51
9	7.83	1.17	1.36	0.17
10	7.54	2.46	6.05	0.80
10	10.73	-0.73	0.53	0.04
8	11.61	-3.61	13.03	1.12
12	11.18	0.82	0.372	0.06
17	15.92	1.09	1.18	0.07
6	4.3	1.7	2.89	0.67
Total				5.702

Degree of freedom = (r-1) (c-1) = (4-1) (4-1) = 9

The table value of χ^2 for the degree of freedom 9 at 5% level of significance is 16.919. The calculated value of χ^2 is 5.702 which is less than the table value, therefore the null hypothesis is **Accepted**. Hence it is inferred there is No Significant between the variables.

Table 6: Correlations for the Conceptual Dimensions and Educational Institutions & Skills Filled by the Students in Engineering Institutions

S.No	Conceptual Dimension	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Business acumen (entrepreneurial)	.0000							
2	Commitment	.10**	.0000						
3	Flexibility	.23**	.04	.0000					
4	Numeracy	.33**	-.02	.04	.0000				
5	Professionalism	-.02	.10**	.08*	.22**	.0000			
6	Technical and computer skills	.18**	.15**	.33**	.10**	.33**	.0000		
7	The ability to solve problems	.33**	.04	.28**	.06*	.27**	.28**	.0000	
8	Tourism knowledge	.34**	.06*	.09*	.04	.5*	.10**	.6*	.0000

Source: Survey Findings

Note: *p<.05, **p<.001

Out of eight independent variables for the select study six variables are found to be significant namely Commitment, Flexibility, Numeracy, Technical and computer skills, the ability to solve problems and Tourism knowledge.

Findings:

In the correlation test out of the eight independent variables for select study six variables are found to be significant namely Commitment, Flexibility, Numeracy, Technical and computer skills, the ability to solve problems and Tourism knowledge. There is no significant relationship between the Gender and the Skill Gap of the Students.

There is a significant relationship between the Age group and the Skill Gap of the Students.

There is no significant relationship between the Career Aspirations and the Skill Gap of the Students.

There is no significant relationship between the Locality of the Students and the Skill Gap of the Students.

There is no significant relationship between the Department/Course and Skill Gap of the Students.

Suggestions:

Getting the campus hiring for the Engineering Educational Institution's students is one of the most vital aspects that is the most expected by the recruiters in India. Students, parents, educational institutions is expecting for the wealthy **Campus Recruitment / Placement Records** as one of the vital parameter in selecting top Engineering Educational Institutions⁶. Following are the suggestions find out from the research's findings:

- ✓ The campus should create a better relationship with the other organizations through MOU, Internship and seminars to the students.
- ✓ The campus hiring program should give the right candidates to the right organizations at the right time in the right place.
- ✓ Employability with better resource has to be given by the Engineering Educational Institutions to the students.
- ✓ Basics of the Campus Recruiting Program should be taught to the students.
- ✓ Engineering Educational Institutions should create a better platform for the career job fair, correct campus hiring program for the best future of the students.
- ✓ The Engineering Educational Institutions should provide right campus job. It should make the students to select right way to catch the right companies at the campus hiring time.
- ✓ By the experience of the campus hiring process the candidates should able to admit their mistakes. The institutions should teach them to accept their mistakes instead of giving wrong answers and making a bad impression in the minds of the recruiters.
- ✓ The institution should create the confident and enthusiastic environment to the students. The organizations also provide its support in this area.
- ✓ The candidates should not lose their courage easily. Sometimes, the interview may go for long time. The best qualities of the candidates may suffer because of their doubting in their potential and nervousness. So the educational institutions should concentrate on this area.

Conclusion:

The corporate recruiting team has taken the Campus Hiring Process from the Engineering Educational Institutions as a part of the strategic planning process. The

⁶ Temponi, C. (2005). Continuous improvement framework: Implications for academia. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 13(1), 17-36

volume of the recruitment/hires is in the need of a new approach for the persons who are really wanted to stay competitive. The organization wants to find the ways to develop/enhance their process of recruitment and it will help to increase the return on investment of the campus hiring. Many campus recruiters are doing this with the help of the successive top Engineering Educational Institutions.

Scope for the Further Research:

In this present study to identify the problems associated with the Skill Gap on the Campus Recruitment in the Educational Institutions in Coimbatore. Similar research studies may be carried out in other Districts and States probed by the future researchers.

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